

Intramolecular Kinetic Isotope Fractionation in the Decomposition of Alkaline Earth Carbonates by 47% Aqueous Hydrobromic Acid. Part II.

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The intramolecular kinetic oxygen isotope fractionation factor, α in the decomposition of the carbonates of strontium and barium by 47% aq. HBr has been determined at temperatures ranging from 25° to 62°. The values have been found to decrease with increase of temperature which has been attributed due to the loosening of the C-O bonds. An empirical relationship between $1000 \ln \alpha$ and temperature has been suggested. The increase of α values with increasing mass of cation of the carbonates has been explained on the basis of the increasing ionic character of the alkaline earths.

A previous paper in this series¹ described the decomposition of calcium carbonate by 47% aq. HBr in the temperature range 25°-62°, the comparison of the kinetic isotope fractionation factor, α with that obtained by 100% phosphoric acid and the empirical relationship between the fractionation factor, α and the temperature of decomposition of the carbonate samples of calcium. In the same continuation the present investigation deals with the determination of α values of the different samples of the carbonates of strontium and barium in the same temperature range with a view to examine the effect of temperature and mass of the cation of the carbonates on the isotopic fractionation factor, α . The possibility of using 47% aq. HBr for the decomposition of the carbonate minerals in preference to the use of 100% phosphoric acid has also been explored.

Experimental

Several carbonate samples of strontium and barium were decomposed by 100% phosphoric acid at 25° by the method described by Sharma et. al.² and Singh et. al.^{3,4} The same samples were also decomposed by 47% aq. HBr at 25°, 30°, 45°, 55° and 62°. The procedure adopted was same of that in our previous communication¹. The carbon dioxide evolved was transferred in sample tubes for mass spectrometric analysis, which was carried out on a 6"-60"-RMS-19 double collecting isotope ratio mass spectrometer designed after Neir⁵ and McKinney et. al.⁶ in the department of chemistry, I. I. T. Kanpur. The isotope

ratio variations has been expressed in terms of δ , where

$$\delta = \left[\frac{(O^{18}/O^{16})_{\text{sample}}}{(O^{18}/O^{16})_{\text{standard}}} - 1 \right] \times 1000$$

The kinetic fractionation factor, α is calculated using the relationship,

$$\alpha = \frac{1 + \delta CO_2/1000}{1 + \delta CO_3^{2-}/1000}$$

in the same way as in our previous papers.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the δ values of carbon dioxide as well as the carbon dioxide yield when the sample were decomposed by 100% phosphoric acid at 25°C. The table also includes the δCO_3^{2-} values calculated on the basis of fractionation factor reported in literature⁷. The carbon dioxide yield and δO^{18} values of carbon dioxide obtained by the decomposition with 47% aq. HBr at the temperature range 25-62° have been presented in table 2. Comparing the carbon dioxide yield of the samples with the theoretically expected yield (6.77 μ moles for SrCO₃ and 5.00 for BaCO₃) it is evident that the samples have nearly 99% of purity.

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TABLE 1— δCO_3^- VALUES CALCULATED FROM δCO_2 OBTAINED BY 100% H_3PO_4 METHOD AT 25°C.

Carbonate	Sample	CO_2 yield in μ moles/mg	δCO_2	Calculated δCO_3^-
SrCO_3	SB 1	6.63	1.34	-8.87
	SB 2	6.70	4.13	-6.11
	SB 3	6.71	5.50	-4.75
	SB 4	6.66	6.90	-3.36
BaCO_3	BC 1	4.92	14.37	3.55
	BC 2	4.95	14.64	3.82
	BC 3	4.93	12.15	1.35
	BC 4	4.97	13.27	2.46

Table 3 shows the enhancement of α values with increasing atomic weight of the metal of the carbonates. This may be explained on the increasing ionic character of the metal atom. As the ionic character increases, the covalent character decreases and the valence electron of the metal is relatively more transferred towards the carbonate ion which strengthens the C-O bond. For a strong C-O bond the lighter isotope is decomposed comparatively faster than the heavier isotope, resulting an increase in the α value. Thus the strength of C-O bond in decreasing order in the alkaline earth carbonates is as $\text{BaCO}_3 > \text{SrCO}_3 > \text{CaCO}_3$.

TABLE 2— δCO_3^- VALUES FOR SrCO_3 and BaCO_3 OBTAINED BY 47% aq. HBr method.

Temp °C	δCO_3^- for SrCO_3				δCO_3^- for BaCO_3			
	SB1	SB2	SB3	SB4	BC1	BC2	BC3	BC4
25	-0.34	2.46	3.85	5.24	12.64	12.93	10.43	11.55
30	-0.47	2.33	3.72	5.11	12.51	12.80	10.30	11.43
36	-0.63	2.17	3.55	4.94	12.35	12.63	10.15	11.26
45	-0.91	1.88	3.23	4.63	12.12	12.39	9.91	11.03
55	-1.21	1.58	2.96	4.45	11.85	12.12	9.63	10.75
62	-1.39	1.39	2.77	4.16	11.66	11.93	9.44	10.56
CO_2 yield μ moles/mg	6.64	6.68	6.70	6.67	4.94	4.93	4.95	4.96

The investigation of intramolecular kinetic fractionation factor α using 47% aq. HBr in the decomposition of alkaline earth carbonates, indicates the possibility of this method to be used in the analysis of $\text{O}^{18}/\text{O}^{16}$ ratio variation in carbonate minerals. The α values, depicted in the form of $1000 \ln \alpha$, for different samples of carbonates of Sr and Ba are shown in table 3. It is quite evident from the above as well as the previous result¹ that α values for a particular carbonate at a particular temperature is almost constant. The error in the measurement is in the fifth place of decimal and therefore it is not affecting the constancy of the α values. The values of α HBr is as precise as that of α H_3PO_4 obtained by Sharma and Sharma⁷. Therefore, in preference to the 100% H_3PO_4 readily available 47% aq. HBr can be safely used in the analysis of $\text{O}^{18}/\text{O}^{16}$ variation in carbonate minerals. The only difficulty encountered in the process is to check the copious fumes of HBr during evacuation, which is achieved by coling the reaction vessel to ice temperature.

The cause for decrease in the values of α with temperature has been attributed to the loosening of C-O bond. With the increase in temperature the C-O bond loosens and so the decomposing reagent finds less distinction between C-O¹⁸ and C-O¹⁶ bonds to break and therefore k_1 , the rate coefficient of decomposition of C-O¹⁶ bond tends to k_2 , the rate coefficient of C-O¹⁸ bond. Since $\alpha = \frac{3k_1}{k_1 + k_2}$, the values of α decreases with the decrease in the values of k_1 and ultimately at infinite temperature $2k_1 \approx k_2$, considering the statistical factor, the α value will tend to 1.

TABLE 3—MEAN VALUES OF $1000 \ln \alpha$ FOR ALKALINE EARTH CARBONATES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES.

Temperature	25°C	30°C	36°C	45°C	55°C	62°C
Mean $1000 \ln \alpha$ for CaCO_3	7.99	7.86	7.69	7.42	7.17	7.00
Mean $1000 \ln \alpha$ for SrCO_3	8.20	8.09	7.92	7.63	7.36	7.18
Mean $1000 \ln \alpha$ for BaCO_3	8.65	8.50	8.35	8.12	7.86	7.68

Further, it is clear that α HBr decreases with temperature. On plotting $1000 \ln \alpha$ against $\frac{1}{T}$ a straight line is obtained, suggesting an empirical relationship, $1000 \ln \alpha = \frac{A}{T} + B$, between fractionation factor α and temperature T. The values for A are 2.67×10^8 , 2.90×10^8 and 2.55×10^8 and that for B are -0.97, -1.48, and 0.09 for CaCO_3 , SrCO_3 and BaCO_3 respectively.

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